

The Stars of Indian Ocean
Arab Navigation

النجوم الملاحة العربية
في المحيط الهندي

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Abbreviations

Curiosities :: Rapoport and Savage-Smith (eds.), *Kitāb gharāʾib al-funūn/The Book of Curiosities*, 2014.

Fawāʾid :: Khoury (ed.), vol. 2 of *al-ʿUlūm al-baḥrīyah ʿinda al-ʿarab*, 1971. Cited by Roman number for the chapter, followed by page number.

Kunitzsch :: Kunitzsch, *Untersuchungen zur Sternnomenklatur der Araber*, 1961.

Muʿjam :: Khoury (ed.), vol. 1-3 of *al-ʿUlūm al-baḥrīyah ʿinda al-ʿarab*, 1971, pp. 142–434.

Staples :: Al-Salimi and Staples, *Maritime Lexicon*, 2019.

Stellung :: Kunitzsch, “Zur Stellung der Nautikertexte Innerhalb der Sternnomenklatur der Araber”, 1967.

Tibbetts :: Tibbetts, *Arab Navigation in the Indian Ocean before the Coming of the Portuguese*, 1971.

Preface

فیتفقّد المعلم الماهر في وسع الفلك وضيق وبعد
النجوم وقربها ونقصان النجوم وزيادتها فيترقى ويبلغ
الغاية ويصوّر العلوم في قلبه ويعرف كيف دوران
الفلك وقياسته على الأنجم في طلوعها وغروبها

“...for the discerning pilot to study the expanse and the compact of the heavenly spheres, the distance and proximity between stars, their increase and their decrease; and thus to reach the ultimate degree, for the sciences to take shape in his heart; and to comprehend the turning and dimensions of the spheres through the stars, as they rise and set.”

Aḥmad ibn Mājid, *Fawā'id* III.

This document has been conceived as a practical and sufficient reference catalogue of the stars, asterisms, and sundry celestial bodies used by early modern Indian Ocean Arab navigators. It is based directly and substantially on the corpus of the two classical representatives of the genre, Aḥmad ibn Mājid and Sulaymān al-Mahrī, but formally it follows closely the organisation and scope of *The Stars of Arab Navigation in Ibn Mājid Works*, a memorable 1990 publication by Ibrahim Khoury.¹

Our primary intention was to digitise the contents of Khoury’s work, in order to make it simply more accessible and searchable, bringing the transliteration up to date and correcting some misprints. Eventually we decided to make the best of some key developments in the field, and we opted for a certain reorganisation of the material and for the introduction of minor additions, drawing from new sources, clarifying information, and hopefully making even more useful what was already a helpful guide. In a way, this is our tribute to Ibrahim Khoury, who is himself a bright star among the scholars of Indian Ocean nautical studies. The following pages draw from his own Introduction to situate the contents of our work.

We would like to thank our colleagues at the RUTTER Project in Lisbon, especially Henrique Leitão, José Manuel Malhão Pereira, and Luis Ribeiro of the *Astra Project*, for their help in the development of this work. We are also grateful to our CIUHCT colleague Samuel Gessner for his insightful comments and suggestions. The weekly meetings of our Lisbon Arabic Reading group have provided us with an invaluable opportunity to discuss

¹ See Bibliography below for all full references. This separata was digitised in October 2020 by Inès Bénard and Juan Acevedo, and it is available in PDF format [following this link](#). For the transliteration, we follow as closely as possible the *ALA-LC Romanization tables*.

many of the astronavigation issues at the basis of this work, and we are particularly grateful to our fellow readers for their enthusiasm and generous expertise. Special thanks to our regulars, Charles Burnett, Eric Staples, Vivian Brown, Razieh-Sadat Mousavi and Nadine Löhr.

Juan Acevedo
Inês Bénard

Introduction

Ibn Mājid and al-Mahrī were from today’s Oman and Yemen respectively, and they were active through the 10th century AH, that is, late 15th and early 16th century AD. They wrote numerous and influential works on maritime sciences in verse and prose,² detailing the principles and application of a very star-centered nautical art. It was a shared Indian Ocean heritage of stellar navigation knowledge, the multinational contours of which are right now being defined by new scholarship, but it is clear that some key features of this early modern system of celestial navigation were articulated and in use, from at least the tenth century, among Persian, Chinese, Indian, Southeast Asian and Arab sailors.³ This transnational knowledge of stellar astronomy trickled into Portuguese nautical literature, and from there it started making its way into French and eventually English and Dutch treatises.⁴ It was approximately one hundred years after Ibn Mājid’s acme, in 1574, that William Bourne published his sea manual, the *Regiment for the Sea* or *Rules of Navigation*, explaining what he called “the new navigation” because it used mathematics and astronomy.⁵

As a matter of fact, Ibn Mājid and al-Mahrī had preceded Bourne and promoted just such “new navigation” before him, approximately between 1462 and 1520, transmitting a wealth of mathematics and astronomy with their nautical art. Ibn Mājid made a very similar claim indeed: “I am writing a new navigation,” he said, “a navigation you never heard of before me”.⁶

This new navigation of Ibn Mājid required, according to himself, a technical knowledge, a good geographical knowledge, including land and seamarks, and especially astronomical learning. In fact, astronomy had extremely varied applications in Ibn Mājid’s New Navigation. The altitudes of stars, their risings and settings, and their relative positions in a rich variety of possible configurations were used: to determine the latitude and thus establish the position of the ship; to estimate the distance that the vessel had travelled; to keep track of time, as a sort of celestial clock; to ascertain the all-important seasons for navigation; and finally, as referents of the nautical compass rhumbs, they were used to determine the course.⁷

We do not intend to examine all these aspects here. Our only purpose is to present

² References to all the related sources and relevant secondary literature can be found in our RUTTER Technical Note, *Indian Ocean Arab Navigation Studies Towards a Global Perspective: Annotated Bibliography and Research Roadmap*.

³ See Shafiq 2013, 99–104; Beaujard 2019, II, 466–7, 479; Varadarajan 2004, 3–18.

⁴ See Bourne 2017, 26–7; Schotte 2019, 100–105.

⁵ “Mathematics”, in this context, means basic notions of cosmography, including calendrical notions, and various types of distance measuring.

⁶ See *al-Balighah fī qiyās al-suhayl wa-al-rāmih*, l. 44—Khoury’s translation.

⁷ See Constable 2012, *passim*; Shihāb 2012, 21–22.

a comprehensive list of the stars mentioned in Ibn Mājid's and al-Mahrī's texts and thus presumably familiar to early modern Arab pilots. Specific textual references are given in the astronomical glossaries of Khoury's publications as mentioned below, particularly his Damascus critical editions of the *Fawā'id* and the *Umdah al-mahrīyah*.

In practice, the astronavigation system is organically tight-knit, interconnected and imbricating in a great many ways, but the two basic sub-systems of reference are the twenty-eight Lunar Stations (*manāzil al-qamar*) and the thirty-two Stellar Rhumbs (*akhnān*). For the purpose of our exposition, we will however classify the celestial objects under the following four categories:

1. The Brightest Stars of the Sky
2. The Stations of the Moon
3. The Stars of Lesser Magnitude
4. The Magellanic Clouds

The main astronomical and uranographic passages in the corpus are: for Ibn Mājid, Chapters 3 and 4 of the *Fawā'id*, and about half of his extant poems, some of which treat of very specific astronavigation issues;⁸ al-Mahrī is notably less astronomical than Ibn Mājid, or rather, often more concerned with calendrical and computus-related questions, and he is certainly less indebted to the medieval uranographical literature. Chapter 2 of his *Umdah*, and Section 2 of his *Minhāj* contain some of the astronomical passages, which are mostly practical in nature, without the often rambling, if engaging, star-lore digressions of Ibn Mājid's *Fawā'id*. The best compendium of these basic sources is Khoury's own *Mu'jam nujūm al-milāḥah* (*Glossary of Navigation Stars*), i.e. pp. 142–434 of the third volume of his *al-'Ulūm al-baḥrīyah 'inda al-'arab*. This is a mostly untapped mine of information which contains comprehensive lists and tables of stars, asterisms and constellations, including discussions of Latin and Greek names and Bayer designations. It is in fact quite evident that the Coimbra booklet used as the basis of this technical note is Khoury's own English summary of the material in his *Mu'jam*.

Main Additional Sources

Apart from Khoury's, some very valuable works have appeared over approximately the last half century, and we have relied on them to help us tackle the often puzzling identification questions. Some treat specifically nautical sources, but others are historical contributions towards clarifying doubts that have been accumulating over many centuries of overlapping astronomical traditions.

⁸ For details, please refer to our previous RUTTER Technical Note, *Indian Ocean Arab Navigation Studies Towards a Global Perspective*, v. 3, Dec. 2020.

Paul Kunitzsch's 1961 *Untersuchungen zur Sternnomenklatur der Araber*, and his 1959 *Arabische Sternnamen in Europa*, are essential references which have remained untranslated, but they address general astronomical topics. Only in some of his later articles did Kunitzsch address specifically the nautical tradition, as shown by an all too brief list of nautical stars published in his 2017 variorum, *The Arabs and the Stars*.

In his 1985 opusculum, "Astronomy for Landlubbers and Navigators: The Case of the Islamic Middle Ages", David King draws attention to some unstudied manuscript sources and to what he calls "Islamic aspects of Islamic science", namely the relations between nautical astronomy and the determination of the qibla, the start of the lunar month and the times of prayers. He also draws attention to the three main historical branches of Arabic astronomy: what he calls mathematical, folk and navigational astronomies. It is unfortunate that no reference to the works by Kunitzsch is made in this work, which addresses so similar topics.

In 2001, Ḥaṣan Ṣāliḥ Shihāb published his *al-Milāḥah al-falakīyah 'inda al-ʿarab* (*Celestial Navigation Among the Arabs*), a small volume which goes over the main features of the system in a concise way, but which in our opinion fails to take full advantage of previous scholarship. One valuable observation worth retaining is the importance of having a proper understanding of pre-modern cosmography in order to study the Arabic nautical tradition.⁹

The 2014 monumental publication of *An Eleventh-century Egyptian Guide to the Universe: the Book of Curiosities (Kitāb gharā'ib al-funūn)* was a spectacular addition to the knowledge of early Arabic uranography. Not only is the organisation of the material remarkably close to the organisation of nautical treatises, but from a scholarly point of view it benefited greatly from the accumulated experience of Kunitzsch at every step, and thus constitutes in a way his last word on Arabic star nomenclature. Though the astronomical scope of this *Guide* goes far beyond astronavigation concerns, we have benefitted from its conscientious explanations at every turn.

In 2017, a major contribution to this field of studies was launched online by Danielle Adams (now at the [Lowell Observatory](#)), the "Two Deserts, One Sky" website, financed by NASA, the University of Arizona and other institutions. Adams draws extensively from the "folk" branch of Arabic astronomical literature, or "Arabian cultural astronomy", including a wealth of pre-Islamic material related to the *anwā'* literature,¹⁰ translating for the first time much early material, and thus giving some context to other parts of the literature which had for decades appeared somehow orphaned in the specialised literature.

Even more recently, Al Salimi and Staples have devoted to "Navigation/*ʿIlm al-milāḥah*"

⁹ P. 14. We are most grateful to the Library of the Oxford Centre for Islamic Studies for helping us access this rare source in spite of the Covid lockdown limitations.

¹⁰ Early genre dealing mostly with meteorological and seasonal astronomy and astrology.

an important chapter of their 2019 *Maritime Lexicon*. They have drawn from an impeccable selection of primary and secondary sources, and added besides very useful and comprehensive illustrations which make directly understandable some of the observational subtleties. Running to more than a hundred pages, this chapter can be considered the most up-to-date addition to our topic in the narrow sense: it is the only English publication devoted specifically to Arabic nautical astronomy. In comparison, and while drawing freely from their work, our present Technical Note means to be a more wieldy and single-minded publication, a quick-reference list, adding a few astronomical precisions here and there and generally a different organisation of the material which we hope will be of immediate practical utility. That is, apart from scholars of the narrowly defined field of Arabic-language nautical literature, we have in mind readers within the field of medieval and early modern Islamic science and culture in general, of the history of astronomy and medieval science more broadly, and of a number of related fields like history of Arabic lexicology and literature; it is a well-known fact that Arabic celestial nomenclature is an important component of astronomical nomenclature in general. With this expanded scope in view, we have added at the end an Astronomical Index which should make it easier to refer to specific celestial objects.

A Reflection on Stellar Navigation Generally

In line with the general aims of the RUTTER Project, a brief reflection on the importance and reach of our theme shall not go amiss. We speak here indistinctly of “astronavigation”, “celestial navigation”, “nautical astronomy” or “astronomical navigation”—the relation established by the pilot between the observation of celestial phenomena and the practical aim of wayfinding—and we have in mind in particular how this conjunction between “what is above”, up in the sky, relates practically to “what is below”, our need for orientation, and how it relates to the concept and the experience of globality.

While it is rightly pointed out that astronomy and navigation have gone hand in hand from their very origins, we have in the European cultural horizon a striking example to bring this notion home: the first work with the explicit title of “Nautical Astronomy” (Ναυτική ἄστρολογία) is attributed to Thales of Miletus (ca. 7th century BC), who is widely considered one of the foundational figures, if not outright “the Father”, of the timeless scientific endeavour we refer to as “philosophy”. This work is sadly not extant, but it is known that it referred to principles of cosmography, to the point that some identify it to a work “On the Solstice and the Equinox”. It is also reported that it spoke of asterisms and nautical distances. This simple fact, even in its vagueness, puts the beginning of Western science right at the door of astronavigation.

This is quite in line with the Platonic view of the importance of astronomy, articulated at its clearest in the *Epinomis*, the *Timaeus* and the *Laws*. For one single example which

should suffice:

“Had we never seen the stars, and the sun, and the heaven,” Timaeus says, “none of the words which we have spoken about the universe would ever have been uttered.... The Divine invented and gave us sight,” he continues, “to the end that we might behold the circuits of the Intellect in the sky, and apply them to the revolutions of our own intelligence, which are akin to them, the unperturbed to the perturbed; and that we, learning from them and partaking by nature of the veracity of calculations, might imitate the utterly unerring circuits of the Divine and regulate our own vagaries.” (*Tim.* 47b5 c4)

In *Epinomis* 976d-e, as in *Timaeus* 47a4, it is made quite clear that the concept number (ἀριθμός), no less, derives from the observation of the heavenly bodies.

This is not the place to elaborate further on the many epistemological consequences of such high regard for stargazing and astronomy, but we shall mention one aspect of it which is too often left aside, probably because we still read Plato with eyes of the Enlightenment, which do away with contemplative dimensions. This, an intimate aspect of celestial navigation is spelt clearly above, as “imitating the circuits... and regulating our own vagaries,” that is, a personal relation between the course of individual life and the observation of the stars. There is undoubtedly, and naturally, a broad human spectrum of possibilities between the cumulative, rational, methodical study of the stars and their inspirational, metalogical and enraptured contemplation.

On this warmer end of the spectrum there is the towering medieval image of Dante, who completes every book of his *Commedia* with the word *stelle*, “stars”. It has been noted that Galileo “considered Dante a peer”, and that for him “the *Divine Comedy* was not a graveyard of discarded astronomical theories, but a poetic prologue to future discoveries.”¹¹

Thinking of early modern times, we may recall the solitary figure of Ignatius of Loyola, a life-long stargazer who looked at the night sky often and for long periods, deriving from the night sky “the greatest consolation.”¹² We should remember that Ignatius’ order, the Society of Jesus, was instrumental in the European consolidation and diffusion of high-level astronomical and cosmographical teachings, contributing directly towards the advent of modern science. The boundary between the two approaches to the night sky is often hard to decide, and it is porous, as many a learned astronomer would acknowledge. In the Islamic tradition—coming back to our Arab authors—the stars are revered as divine signs and followed as guides “through the dark of land and sea” (Qur’ān 6:97). Only if we keep in mind this dual approach to the night sky, by bringing observation and observance back to

¹¹ Daugherty 2019, 26.

¹² McEvoy 2021, 17.

their common origin,¹³ only then can we start to understand the fundamental pre-modern attitude towards the stars, either East or West, ancient or medieval, and to make sense of our epigraph by Ibn Mājid, and those “sciences taking shape in the heart”.

“E quindi uscimmo a riveder le stelle”
(“And then did we emerge to see the stars,” *Commedia* XXXIV, 139)
Bodleian Library MS. Holkham misc. 48, p. 54.

¹³ With thanks to Samuel Gessner for bringing this to our attention.

THE FOLLOWING LISTS of 155 stars, combined in 111 asterisms and celestial objects, are meant to show the richness of the “material” of early modern Arab pilots. We hope they may also give glimpses into the complexity of the astronavigation system which put these elements into many relations of different kinds. Details of the historical developments and variations within this transmitted mass of astronomical lore can be found mostly in the works by Kunitzsch. Details of their practical usage for sailing, including 19th and 20th-century examples and references, can be found primarily in Al Salimi and Staples’ *Lexicon*, 2019; Harriet *et al.*, 2017; and Facey and Constable (eds), *The Principles of Arab Navigation*, 2012.

1 Brightest Stars of the Sky

The following Arabic names correspond to twenty-three of the brightest stars of the sky, as they were used by Arabic navigators in the fifteenth century.¹⁴

1. al-Shi‘rá الشعري: α CMa, Sirius. Also known as al-Shi‘r and al-Shi‘rā’; most often al-Shi‘rá al-‘Abūr العبري الشعري (The Sirius Which Passed Over [the Milky Way]) or al-Tīr التير; rarely, al-Bājis الباجس or al-Bājis al-Awwal. According to Ibn Mājid (IV, 153), al-Tīr was an Arabicized Persian name used by the *ahl al-baḥr*, “the people of the sea”.¹⁵ Al-Bājis (The Stream Opener) was the name given by the people of Yemen.
2. Suhayl سهيل (The Little Easy One): α Car, Canopus. Also known as Miqdāf al-Safīnah مقداف السفينة (The Oar of the Ship), or Miqdāf al-Safā’in مقداف السفائن (The Oar of the Ships).
3. al-Ma‘qil المعقل (The Fortress): β Cen, Hadar, but sometimes also α Cen, Rigil Kentaurus, i.e., one of the Ḥimarān. It therefore corresponds to either al-Wazn الوزن (The Weight) or al-Ḥaḍarī الحضري (The Settled One), from which the modern name Hadar derives. al-Ma‘qil seems to be a specifically nautical name, not found in astronomical sources.
4. al-Simāk al-Rāmiḥ الرامح السماك (The Spear-Bearing Sky-Raiser): α Boo, Arcturus. Also known as al-Rāmiḥ al-Janūbī (The Southern Spearman), or al-Mu‘tālī المعتلي (The Raised One), or simply as al-Rāmiḥ (The Spear-Bearing), and also as al-Uḥaymir الأحيمر (The Little Red One) and Simāk al-Shamālī (The Northern Sky-Raiser).
5. al-Kāsir الكاسر (The Falling One): α Lyr, Vega. Also known as: al-Nasr al-Kāsir نسر الكاسر (The Falling Eagle), al-Nasr al-Kabīr (The Big Eagle), al-Nasr al-Kafīt (The Open-

¹⁴ Khoury refers to *Norton Atlas*, 17th edition, 1978, p. 89, for this choice of “the twenty-five stars”, but the question of a specific number of “nautical stars” is a sprawling topic in itself. In modern recensions, the decisive influence seems to have been Maskelyne’s 1767 publication of the first *Nautical Almanac*, and specifically the *Requisite Tables*, listing fifty-eight or sixty “selected stars”. See our Bibliography below for further details.

¹⁵ See Tolmacheva 1980, 186–89, for more on the linguistic Persian influence.

- Winged Eagle), al-Nasr al-Wāqī‘ (Standing Eagle), al-Wāqī‘ (The Standing One), Najm al-Nasr (Star of the Eagle), al-Nasr (The Eagle), Nasr al-Shām (Northern Eagle). There is a philological case for translating *nasr* as “vulture” (Adams; Lane), but using *nasr* takes into account also the ancient Greek related constellation of the Eagle. According to Khoury’s glossary on al-Mahrī, and to Tibbetts, this star was also called al-Kāthir الكاثر (The Abundant).
6. al-Nājid al-Barrāq الناجد البراق (The Supporting Bright One): β Ori, Rigel (Foot), though sometimes it can refer to Rigel and Saiph (βκ Orionis), which together represent the two feet of Orion. Other names: al-Barrāq al-Nājid, Rijl al-Jawzā’ رجل الجوزاء (Foot of Jawzā’).¹⁶
 7. al-‘Ayyūq العيوق (The Goat): α Aur, Capella: Other names for this star: al-Bārr البائر (The Devotee), Bārr al-Thurayyā بارّ الثريا (The Devotee of Thurayyā), ‘Ayyūq al-Thurayyā (The Goat of Thurayyā). Curiosities gives the unusual reading al-Bāz الباز (The Falcon). The meaning of “goat”, as in the Latin and Greek names, may go back to early Semitic star-lore (see Kunitzsch).
 8. al-Shi‘rā al-Shāmīyah الشعري الشامية (The Northern Sirius): α CMi, Procyon, called also al-Shi‘rā al-Ghumaysā’ الغميصاء (The Bleary-eyed Sirius), or simply al-Ghumaysā’. Counted together with Sirius, these two stars receive the unexpected title of al-Shi‘rayān الشعريان, “The Two Shi‘ras”, i.e. “The Two Sirii” (“Siriuses” perhaps?).
 9. al-Muḥannith المحنث (The Oathbreaker): α Eri, Achernar. In nautical literature it is uniquely called also Sillibār سلّبار.¹⁷
 10. Ḥaḍār حظار (meaning unknown): β Cen, Hadar or Agena. Also as Ḥazār حظار (The Breakwater), or called al-Zalīm الظليم (The Male Ostrich), Zalīm al-Ma‘qil (The Ostrich of the Fortress), Zalīm al-Ḥimārayn (The Ostrich of the Two Donkeys), al-Ḍifdi‘ al-Mu’akhkhar المؤخر الضفدع (The Trailing Frog). It is often paired with al-Wazn, α Cen; see below the [entry for al-Ḥimarān](#).
 11. al-Ṭā’ir الطائر (The Flying One): α Aql, Altair. It is also known by these other names: al-Nasr al-Ṣaghīr النسر الصغير (The Small Eagle), al-Nasr al-Ṭā’ir (The Flying Eagle), al-Nasr al-Ṭalīq النسر الطليق (The Outstretched Eagle), al-Nasr al-Yamānī (The Southern Eagle), and al-Hīrān الهيران (meaning unknown).
 12. al-Dabarān الدبران (The One Behind): α Tau, Aldebaran. It has many other names: al-Tābi‘ التابع (The Follower) or al-Tuwaybi‘ (The Little Follower), al-Burkān or Barkān البركان (The Volcano), al-Ba‘īr الباعر (The Camel), Tālī al-Najm تالي النجم (Follower of the Pleiades) and just short al-Tālī, al-Ḥādī الحادي (The Camel Driver), Ḥādī al-Najm (The Driver of the Star), al-Dubayr (The Little One Behind), al-Mijdaḥ or al-Mujdaḥ

¹⁶ See below, [Gemini](#), about the ancient Arabic name of Jawzā’.

¹⁷ This is Khoury’s vocalisation, but also found as Silibār, Sulbār and Salbār. See Kunitzsch 1977, an article solely devoted to this star.

- المجدح (The Rain Stirrer). There is a related variant al-Miḥḍaj المجدح in some of Ibn Mājid's works which appears to be a compounded scribal mistake (*taṣhīf*), see Khoury (*Mu'jam* 352). Together with α Ori, Betelgeuse, they are both referred to as al-Aḥmarān الأحمران (The Two Red Ones).
13. al-Murabba' المرّبع (The Square): α Cru, Acrux. Ibn Mājid said it is called al-Taḥṭānī التحتاني (The Lower One), al-Murabba' al-Taḥṭānī (The Lower Square), al-Murabba' al-Taḥṭī (same meaning), al-Najm al-Taḥṭānī min al-Murabba' (The Lower Star of the Square), Anjum al-Murabba' al-Qarībāt min al-Mā' الماء من المرّبع القريبات من الماء (The Stars of the Square Which are Close to the Water).
 14. al-Mirzam المرزم (meaning uncertain): mostly refers to γ Ori, Bellatrix, but occasionally identified with α Ori, Betelgeuse too. Called also Mirzam al-Jawzā' مرزم الجوزاء, Najm al-Jawzā' (The Star of Jawzā'), Yad al-Jawzā' al-Yamanī يد الجوزاء اليمني (The Southern Hand of Jawzā'), or al-Marām المرام (Longing). Both stars were also called Yadā al-Jawzā' (The Two Hands of Jawzā'). Mirzam is an ancient name which seems to have been used for any of three different stars that accompanied one of three "Siriuses" (Shi'rá), on the principle that "each Sirius has a Mirzam"; this means it was β CMa or β CMi or γ Ori (see Kunitzsch 78).
 15. al-Qalb القلب (The Heart): α Sco, Antares, named also Qalb al-'Aqrab قلب العقرب (The Heart of the Scorpion), al-'Aqrab (The Scorpion) and Najm al-Qalb (The Star of the Heart).
 16. al-Simāk al-A'zal الأعزل السماء (The Unarmed Sky-Raiser): α Vir, Spica. Also al-A'zal (The Unarmed), al-A'zal al-Ṭayyāsh الطيّاش (The Most Fickle Unarmed One ??), and al-Janūbī (The Southern One). It is associated with α Boo, Arcturus, al-Simāk al-Rāmiḥ الرامح السماء (The Armed Sky-Raiser). The name Simāk is explained by the eminent grammarian and lexicographer Sibawayh as related to its "elevation" (*irtifā'*, probably both in a subjective and objective meaning); this meaning is confirmed by Ibn Mājid (*Fawā'id* III, 73–80).
 17. Ra's al-Taw'am al-Mu'akhkhar رأس التوأم المؤخر (The Head of the Rear Twin): β Gem, Pollux. It forms part of the 7th lunar station, al-Dhirā'.
 18. Ākhir al-Nahr آخر النهر (The End of the River): α PisA, Fomalhaut. Known by several other names: Awākhir al-Mā' أواخر الماء (The Last Ones of the Water), Awākhir al-Nahr, Awwal al-Nahr (The First One of the River), al-Sākib الساكب (The Pourer), Sākib al-Mā' (The Water Pourer), al-Ḍifdi' al-Awwal الأول الضفدع (The First Frog) or Ḍifdi' al-Muqaddam (Foremost Frog), Ḍifdi' al-Sākib (The Frog of the Pourer), Ḍifdi' Sākib al-Mā' (The Frog of the Water Pourer), al-Ḍafādi' (The Frogs), Fam al-Ḥūt al-Janūbī فم الحوت الجنوبي (The Mouth of the Southern Fish), Fam al-Ḥūt al-Yamanī (The Mouth of the Southern Fish), Fam al-Samak al-Janūbiyyah (The Mouth of the Southern Fish),

- al-Zalīm al-Fard **الظليم الفرد** (The Solitary Ostrich), al-Zalīm Sākib al-Mā' (The Ostrich of the Water Pourer). It must be noted that the modern name Achernar, though derived from this star, was assigned in fact to α Eridani, known in Arabic as al-Muḥannith and as Sillibār, *see above*.
19. al-Ridf **الردف** or al-Radīf **الرديف** (The Follower): α Cyg, Deneb. Synonyms: Ridf al-Dajājah **ردف الدجاجة** (The Chicken's Follower), Ridf al-Majarraḥ **ردف المجرة** (The Galaxy's Follower), al-Ridf al-Munīr (The Bright Follower), al-Ridf al-Mu'akhhkar (The Latter Follower), al-Munīr min Nujūm al-Dajājah (The Brightest of the Chicken's Stars), al-Ridf al-Fawāris **الردف الفوارس** (The Follower of the Riders [i.e. $\delta\gamma\epsilon\zeta$ Cyg]), Najm al-Dajājah (The Star of the Chicken). This star is also called sometimes Shalyāq **شلياق** (Lyre) by Ibn Mājid.
20. Najm al-Ṣalīb al-Sharqī **نجم الصليب الشرقي** (The Eastern Star of the Cross): β Cru, Mimosa, one of al-Mashriqiyāt min al-Murabba' **المشريقيات من المربع** (The Eastern Ones of the Square).
21. al-Fu'ād **الفؤاد** (The Liver): in nautical literature it refers to α CVn, Cor Caroli, and not to Regulus. The confusion arises from the existence among early Arabs of a megaconstellation called al-Asad (see Adams) which was then eventually assimilated to a certain extent with the Ptolemaic Lion. It is also called Fu'ād al-Asad **فؤاد الأسد** (The Liver of the Lion), Qalb al-Asad (The Heart of the Lion); Fu'ād al-Layth **فؤاد الليث** (The Liver of the Lion), and al-Malakī **الملكي** (The Royal One).
22. al-Shawlah **الشولة** (The Raised Tail): λ Sco, Shaula. Also Shawlat al-'Aqrab (The Raised Tail of the Scorpion), al-Shawl (The Raised Tail), al-Ibraḥ **الإبرة** (The Sting). See below, [Lunar Station 19](#) of the same name.
23. Kalbā al-Dabarān **كلبا الدبران** (The Two Dogs of Aldebaran): $\nu\kappa$ Tau, “two little stars between the Pleiades and Aldebaran” (see Kunitzsch 74). Also called simply al-Kalbān (The Two Dogs).

2 The Lunar Stations (*Manāzil al-Qamar*)¹⁸

As is customary in astronomical literature, Ibn Mājid divides the Stations into Northern and Southern, giving the number of stars in each of them. These descriptions occasionally vary across his different works, as will be evident below. Remarkably, al-Mahrī elaborates significantly less on this topic, with only one section in his *Minhāj* devoted to it.

The main Arabic nautical sources for the *Manāzil* are Chapter 3 of Ibn Mājid's *Fawā'id*, Section 2 of his *Hāwiyah*, his poems *Manāzil al-qamar*, and *Al-Qāfiyah fī ma'rifat al-*

¹⁸ The use of English “mansion”, though customary, is an overly literal translation of the Latin *mansio*, meaning simply a stopover, a way station, even an abode or lodge, but without connotations of grandeur. By perhaps significant contrast, the twelve solar zodiac constellations are called *burūj*, “castles, fortresses”.

majhūlāt min al-nujūm. For al-Mahri, we refer to Section 7 of his *Minhāj*.

A general alternative name for the Lunar Stations is *Nujūm al-Akhdh*, “stars of entrance”, because every night the moon enters (*ya’khadhu fī*, see Lane s.v. ²-*kh-dh*), seizes, comes into temporary possession of, a part of the sky.

2.1 The Northern Stations

They are fourteen:

1. al-Sharaṭān الشيطان (The Two Beginnings):¹⁹ βγ Ari or, less commonly, αβγ Ari. Most authors agree it refers to βγ Ari, only two stars (*kawkabān*), which not only explains the dual form of the name, but also agrees with the corresponding Indian *nakshatra*, Ashvini. Ibn Mājid does not apparently distinguish al-Sharaṭān from al-Nāṭḥ (The Butting), or al-Nāṭiḥ (The Butting One), as the astronomers (*viz.* Ibn Qutaybah, al-Ṣūfī and al-Bīrūnī) do; for him al-Nāṭḥ النطح is also called al-Fard al-Kabīr (The Big Solitary One) and corresponds to α Ari alone.²⁰ al-Bīrūnī specifies that when “a third nearby star is added”, the proper name should be al-Ashrāṭ (The Beginnings—i.e. not a dual). In modern nomenclature, the name Sheratan is used to refer to β Ari.
2. al-Buṭayn البطين (The Little Belly): εδρ Ari. It was also called Baṭn al-Ḥamal بطن الحمل (The Belly of the Ram), or simply al-Baṭn (The Belly). In modern nomenclature, δ Ari is officially named Botein.
3. al-Thurayyā الثريا (The Little Abundant One): M45, the Pleiades. The usual alternative name, al-Najm النجم, seems to actually make of the Pleiades “The Star” par excellence. It figures prominently in pre-Islamic poetry. In *Fawā'id* III, 37, it is also called al-Jām الجام and al-Lijām اللجام, which are explained as Persian names. Other astronomical sources call it Alyat al-Ḥamal ألية الحمل (The Tail of the Ram).
4. al-Dabarān الدبران (The One Behind [the Pleiades]): α Tau, Aldebaran. Also known as Tābi‘ al-Najm تابع النجم and Tālī al-Najm (both meaning The Follower of the Star). A number of other alternative names exist, see above, Brightest Stars in the Sky, no. 12.
5. al-Haq‘ah الهقعة or al-Haq‘ الهقع (A Tuft of Horse Hair): λφ¹⁻² Ori. This station was also known as Ra’s al-Jawzā’ رأس الجوزاء (Head of Jawzā’). Ibn Majid partly identifies it with “The Giant” (al-Jabbār الجبار, Orion).
6. al-Han‘ah الهنعة or al-Han‘c الهنع (The Neck Mark): also called al-Taḥīyah (The Greeting). A group of two to five or six stars in a curved shape “like the letter *nūn* ن”: γημνξι Gem or εγζλδ Gem. Earlier astronomical literature, like al-Mahrī, distinguishes between al-Han‘ah as composed of two stars only, γξ Gem, and four other stars called al-Taḥāyī التحايي (The Greeting Ones), ημνι Gem, but this last name is used occasionally also for

¹⁹ See Kunitzsch 110.

²⁰ It should be noted that according to modern nomenclature, the derived Arabic name, Elnath, refers not to the stars in this lunar station, but to β Tauri.

- the previous lunar station, al-Haq‘ah. The corresponding Indian *nakshatra*, Ardra, is identified in the earliest system by γ Gem (Abhyankar 1990), the star called Alhena in modern nomenclature, straight after this station’s name.
7. al-Dhirā‘ الذراع (The Forearm [of the Lion]): $\alpha\beta$ Gem, Castor and Pollux, sometimes with the addition of Procyon and Gomeisa, $\alpha\beta$ CMi. There is an astronomical tradition that “The Forearm means always two stars,” and accordingly divisions are established between the two pairs mentioned above, al-Dhirā‘ al-Shāmī (The Northern Forearm) and al-Dhirā‘ al-Yamānī (The Southern Forearm). The same distinction is also made between al-Dhirā‘ al-Mabsūṭah المبسوطة الذراع (The Extended Forearm) and al-Dhirā‘ al-Maqbūḍah المقبوضة الذراع (The Drawn-up Forearm). From here to 11, all the station names refer to parts of The Lion.
 8. al-Nathrah النثرة (The Sneeze): ε Cnc/M44, Praesepe. A station described as dimly visible or nebulous, most likely referring to the lesser magnitude stars of Cancer and the Beehive Cluster, M44, compared to the droplets of a sneeze. More specifically found as Nathrat al-Asad (The Sneeze of the Lion). Variations, found in Ibn Mājid and earlier authors, associate the station’s name with $\gamma\delta\varepsilon$ Cnc, or specify that $\gamma\delta$ Cnc are the two nostrils, while ε Cnc would be the tip of the nose.
 9. al-Ṭarf الطرف (The Gaze): χ Cnc + λ Leo, or λ Leo + κ Cnc, or also $\varepsilon\theta$ Leo. Found explicitly as Ṭarf al-Asad (The Gaze of the Lion), with an explanation that it refers to the smallness of the eyes of the lion. In any case it seems accepted that the station is composed by two stars.
 10. al-Jabhah الجبهة (The Forehead): $\zeta\eta\alpha$ Leo, named also Jabhat al-Asad (The Forehead of the Lion). The southernmost star of the asterism is Regulus, α Leo. The official name of γ Leo, Algieba, derives from this station.
 11. al-Zubrah الزبرة (The Mane): $\delta\theta$ Leo. Also, Zubrat al-Asad (The Mane of the Lion), al-Khirātān الخراتان, al-Kharātān, or-Khurtān الخرتان, meaning The Two Hollows (on the flanks of the lion), whence the modern official name of θ Leo, Chertan.
 12. al-Ṣarfah الصرفة (The Change): β Leo, named al-Ṣarf, Dhanab al-Asad ذنب الأسد (The Tail of the Lion), whence the modern name Denebola; also called al-Qunb القنب (The Sheath of the Penis).
 13. al-‘Awwā’ العواء (The Howler): $\beta\eta\gamma\delta\varepsilon$ Vir. Ibn Mājid adds $\sigma\pi$ Vir to make it seven stars, while others only use four, $\beta\eta\gamma\varepsilon$ Vir, or $\eta\gamma\delta\varepsilon$ Vir. It is said to resemble the Arabic letters *lām* ل or *kāf* ك. The name al-‘Awwā’ has been explained as dogs howling at The Lion, or at the cold (?) weather, or as referring to the curved shape of the asterism. In any case it gave rise to the formal name of δ Vir, Minelauva, an adaptation of *min al-‘awwā’*, “from the ‘Awwā’”. Some authors give al-Ṣayyāḥ الصيَّاح (The Clamorous Man) as an alternative name for this station, but it is more appropriately used for the

constellation of Bootes.

14. al-Simāk al-Aʿzal السماك الأعزل (The Unarmed Sky-Raiser): α Vir, Spica, sometimes called in Arabic Sunbulah سنبله, The Ear of Wheat, as a direct translation of the Greek and Latin names. For more details, see above, the Brightest Stars of the Sky, no. 16. Together with the other Simāk, Arcturus, the Simākān سماكان (the two Simāk) are also known as Sāqā al-Asad ساقا الأسد (The Shanks of the Lion).

2.2 The Southern Stations

They are fourteen also.

15. al-Ghafr الغفر (The Tail Tuft): this name refers to $\kappa\lambda$ Vir,²¹ or to λ Vir, Khambalia, alone. The name is explained (Khoury, *Muʿjam*, 237; Kunitzsch 63) as meaning *ghafrah*, “the hair at the tip of the Lion’s tail”.
16. al-Zubānā الزباني (The Claw [of the Scorpion]): $\alpha\beta$ Lib. Also, with the same meaning, al-Zabn الزبن, al-Zubān الزبان, or al-Zubānayān الزبانين (The Two Claws), referring to the southern and the northern one, al-Zubānā al-Janūbī and al-Zubānā al-Shamālī. The modern names Zubenelgenubi and Zubenelschamali derive from this station.
17. al-Iklīl الإكليل (The Crown): $\beta\delta\pi$ Sco, three stars on the forehead of the Scorpion. Named also Iklīl al-Janūbī (The Southern Crown), Iklīl al-ʿAqrab, Iklīl al-ʿAqrabī (The Scorpion’s Crown) or al-Tāj التاج (The Crown). These three stars would represent not just the crown, but also the head of the Scorpion which, in some sources, may be defined simply as β Sco—a star called today Acrab, straight from the Arabic ʿaqrab (scorpion).
18. al-Qalb القلب (The Heart): α Sco, Antares, named Qalb al-ʿAqrab قلب العقرب (The Heart of The Scorpion) too. Cf. no. 15 of the Brightest Stars in the Sky.
19. al-Shawlah الشولة (The Raised Tail): usually only two stars, $\lambda\nu$ Sco, Shaula and Lesath. Named also al-Shūl, Shawlat al-ʿAqrab (The Raised Tail of The Scorpion), and al-Ibrah (The Sting), though this is more properly considered to be “a spot of fog” (*laṭkhat ghaym*), corresponding to M7, the Ptolemy Cluster. Ibn Mājid says that al-Shawlah is a group of small stars shaped like the Arabic letter *nūn* ن, probably $\lambda\nu\kappa\iota\theta$ Sco. Cf. the Brightest Stars of the Sky, no. 22.
20. al-Naʿāʾim النعائم (The Ostriches) or al-Naʿām النعام: $\gamma\delta\epsilon\eta\sigma\phi\tau\zeta$ Sgr. According to *al-Fawāʾid*, these eight stars represent two groups of ostriches approaching (*al-Wāridah*) and leaving (*al-Ṣādirah*) the river of the Milky Way.
21. al-Baldah البلدة (The Place): most commonly identified with an empty space east of al-Naʿāʾim, and sometimes with al-Udhī الأُدحي, “the nest of the ostriches”, which represents a group from four to six stars, roughly $\xi\sigma\pi\rho\nu$ Sgr. This group is also called

²¹ Variations like $\iota\chi\lambda$ or $\iota\theta\lambda$ Vir do not make sense astronomically and are most likely due to nomenclature confusion.

- at times al-Qilādah الفلادة, “The Necklace”.
22. Sa’d al-Dhābiḥ سعد الذابح (The Omen of The Sacrificer): $\alpha\beta$ Cap, Algedi and Dabih. Ibn Mājid explains that Dhābiḥ can also mean “the slaughtered one”, and in one of his poems he adds a third faint star. There are ten ancient Arab asterisms called Sa’d (pl. Su’ūdāt), thought to refer to the name of a very early Middle Eastern deity, possibly Babylonian (Kunitzsch 100). The use of “omen” is meant to retain the potential ambiguity as either auspicious or inauspicious.
 23. Sa’d Bula’ سعد بلع (The Voracious Omen): $\nu\mu\epsilon$ Aqr, sometimes only $\mu\epsilon$ Aqr. Called also simply Bula’ (Voracious).
 24. Sa’d al-Su’ūd سعد السعود (The Omen of Omens): $\beta\xi$ Aqr. Sometimes a third star is added, either λ Cap or c Cap. Sadalsuud is used in modern nomenclature for β Aqr.
 25. Sa’d al-Akhbiyah سعد الأخبية (The Omen of the Woolen Tents): $\gamma\pi\zeta\eta$ Aqr. Four stars said to resemble the foot of a duck, or a group of tents. γ Aqr, the first of the four stars, is referred to by modern nomenclature as Sadachbia.
 26. al-Fargh al-Muqaddam فرغ المقدم (The Front Spout [of the Bucket]): $\alpha\beta$ Peg, Markab and Scheat, the two western stars of the Square of Pegasus. Also called Farghān al-Muqaddamān (The Two Front Spouts) and al-Fargh al-Awwal (The First Spout). Regarding the image of the Bucket and Pegasus, see below the [entry for Pegasus](#).
 27. al-Fargh al-Mu’akhkhar فرغ المؤخر (The Rear Spout): γ Peg + α And (= δ Peg), Algenib and Alpheratz, the two eastern stars of the Square of Pegasus. Also called al-Fargh al-Thānī (The Second Spout) and al-Fargh al-Akhir (The Last Spout).
 28. Baṭn al-Ḥūt بطن الحوت (The Belly of the Fish): β And, Mirach. It is also called Baṭn al-Ḥūt al-Shamālī (The Belly of the Northern Fish), Qalb al-Ḥūt قلب الحوت (The Heart of the Fish), al-Rishā’ الرشاء (The Rope), and Baṭn al-Samakah (The Belly of the Fish). Al-Ḥūt is normally used for the Ptolemaic constellation of Pisces.

3 Zodiacal Constellations

We list here some zodiacal stars which are of lesser magnitude or which have separate nautical use apart from their asterisms.

Aries: Ari · al-Hamal (The Lamb), al-Kabsh (The Ram)

1. al-Adlā’ الأضلاع (The Ribs): 41(c), 39, 35, 33 Ari, called also Adlā’ al-Ḥamal (The Ribs of the Lamb) or Adlā’ al-Kabsh (The Ribs of the Ram).
2. Awwal Adlā’ al-Ḥamal (The First of the Ribs of the Lamb): 41(c) Ari. Synonyms: al-Ḍil’ الضلع (The Rib), al-Ḍil’ al-Saḥābī, al-Ḍil’ al-Shām (The Northern Rib), al-Ḍil’ al-Shamālī (The Northern Rib), al-Ḍil’ al-Kabīr al-Munawwar (The Big Luminous Rib), al-Ḍil’ al-Munīr (The Bright Rib), or al-Munīr min al-Ḍilū’ المنير من الضلوع (The Bright

One Among the Ribs). Staples identifies al-Ḍilʿ al-Munīr with γ And, while Tibbetts speculates it may refer to α Per.

3. Fard al-Sharaṭayn فرد الشرطين (The Solitary One of the Two Beginnings): α Ari, Ḥamal. Named also al-Fard al-Kabīr (The Big Solitary One), Fard al-Naḥḥ (The Solitary One of the Butting), al-Fard min al-Naḥḥ (The Solitary from the Butting).

Taurus: Tau · Thawr (Bull)

1. al-Ḍayqah الضيقة (The Narrows): χν Tau. Also vocalised as al-Dīqah. Ibn Mājid speaks of “a gap (فرجة *furjah*) between Aldebaran and the Pleiades” which is identified to the “two stars” mentioned above and located in the same place by earlier astronomers (Khoury, *Muʿjam* 324).
2. Qalāʾiṣ فلائص (The Young Camels): Hyades. They are at times described as stars surrounding al-Dabarān, and called Ghanīmāt al-Dabarān غنيمات الدبران (The Spoils of Aldebaran). Khoury specifies (*Muʿjam* 346) that there are two different asterisms of this name; the second is also called Qilādah, in Sagittarius, see below.

Gemini: Gem · Tawʾamān (The Twins)

A very common name for Gemini in the medieval astronomical tradition is al-Jawzāʾ الجوزاء, but in the nautical literature, as in early Arabic folk astronomy, this name refers to al-Jabbār الجبار, The Giant, i.e. Orion.

1. Shāmī al-Dhirāʿ al-Shāmī شمالي الذراع الشمالي (The Northern One of the Northern Foreleg): α Gem, Castor. Other names are Shāmī al-Shām, and Shāmī al-Shāmī.

Virgo: Vir · al-Sunbulah (The Ear of Wheat)/ al-ʿAdhrāʾ (The Virgin)

Using Sunbulah for the name of the constellation seems to be an extension of the name of Spica, its brightest star, but it is also used by the astronomers and Ibn Mājid himself to refer to Coma Berenices (al-Hulbah/al-Ḍafīrah).

1. Ākhir al-ʿAwwāʾ آخر العوّاء (The Last One of the Howlers): ε Vir, Vindemiatrix.
2. Awwal al-ʿAwwāʾ أول العوّاء (The First One of the Howlers): ο Vir.
3. Zāwiyat al-ʿAwwāʾ زاوية العوّاء (The Corner of the Howlers): γ Vir, Porrima. This name is sometimes associated to η Vir.

Sagittarius: Sgr · Al-Qaws (The Bow)

1. al-Sahm السهم or Sahm al-Qaws (The Arrow of the Bow): γ Sgr, Alnasl or Nushaba. The name can also refer to αβ Grui. The modern name Alnasl derives from the Arabic *naṣl*, “arrowhead”, which would be an abbreviation from the Almagest name Naṣl al-Qaws نصل القوس (The Arrowhead of the Bow). Modern Nushshābah would also derive from the Arabic expression *zujj al-nushshābah*, translated as “The Tip of the Arrow”.

It is important to note that these “arrows” related to Sagittarius have no relation with the constellation of Sagitta.

2. Sahn al-Awwal (The First of the Arrow): φ Sgr. See Khoury (*Mu‘jam* 312) for details of this identification, which in any case seems based directly on al-Mahrī. Kunitzsch (“Zur Stellung der Nautikertexte...”, 62–3), however, explains that it has to refer to γ Gru, Aldhanab.
3. al-Şādirah الصادرة (The Arriving Ones): $\sigma\phi\tau\zeta$ Sgr, viz. al-Na‘ā’im al-Şādirah (The Arriving Ostriches). See also above, [Lunar Station 20](#).
4. al-Qilādah القلادة (The Necklace): $\xi\sigma\pi\delta\rho\nu$ Sgr. Sometimes also called Qalā’iṣ (The Young Camels), but see [above under Taurus](#), and [Lunar Station 21](#), al-Baldah.
5. al-Na‘ā’im al-Wāridah الوارءة النعائم (The Departing Ostriches): $\gamma\delta\epsilon\eta$ Sgr. Also simply al-Wāridah (The Departing). See also above, [Lunar Station 20](#).
6. Taḥtah al-Qaws تط القوس (Below the Bow), σ Sgr, Nunki. Khoury (*Mu‘jam* 268–9) elaborates in detail about the confusion between this name and Taḥta al-Faras تحت الفرس (Below the Horse) or Faḥat al-Qaws (The Opening of the Bow).

Aquarius: Aqr · al-Dalū (The Bucket), Sākib al-Mā’ (Water Pourer)

The name al-Dalū الدلو is often used in nautical works to refer to the Great Square of Pegasus.

1. Sa‘d al-Malik سعد الملك (The Royal Omen): $\alpha\omicron$ Aqr.

4 Non-zodiacal Constellations

The stars in this section, all of practical importance in navigation, are grouped according to their position within Ptolemaic constellations, and by their latitude north or south of the ecliptic.

4.1 Northern Constellations

Ursa Minor: UMi · Dubb al-Aṣghār (The Little Bear)

1. al-Jāh الجاه: α UMi, Polaris. It is named al-Judayy الجديّ (The Little Kid) or Jady Banāt Na‘sh بنات نعش (The Kid of the Daughters of the Bier), thus to distinguish it from the other Jady (i.e. Capricornus), from which the name only differs in vocalisation (see Kunitzsch 62). It is also called al-Sumayyā السميّا (The Little Celestial One), and Najm al-Qutb نجم القطب (The Star of the Pole).
2. al-Farqadān الفرقدان (The Two Calves): $\beta\gamma$ UMi. A very prominent pair of stars, also called al-Ḥājizān الحاجزان (The Two Deterrents), and often found in verse as al-Farāqid الفراقء (The Calves). They are often called The Guardians, because they are said to watch over, to circumambulate (*yaṭūfūna*) the Polar Star.

3. al-Farqad al-Kabīr الفرفد الكبير (The Big Calf): β UMi, Kochab, called al-Kabīr (The Big One), Farqad al-Akbar (The Bigger Calf), al-Farqad (The Calf) and Muqaddam al-Farqad (The Foremost Calf) too.
4. al-Farqad al-Ṣaghīr (The Small Calf): γ UMi, Pherkad. Called also simply al-Ṣaghīr (The Little One).

Ursa Major: UMa · al-Na‘sh (The Bier); al-Dubb al-Akbar (The Big Bear)

The first seven stars of UMa, “The Seven Famous Ones”, al-Sab‘ah al-Mash’hūrah السبعة المشهورة, are named al-Na‘sh or Na‘sh as Samā’ (The Celestial Bier), al-Na‘sh al-Kubrā (The Great Bier) or, very often too, Banāt Na‘sh (The Girls/Daughters of the Bier). Some of them are combined into smaller asterisms with particular and rather macabre names: αβ are called Awwalān al-Na‘sh (The Two First of the Bier) or Muqaddamān al-Na‘sh (The Two Foremost of the Bier), or al-Awā’il al-Nu‘ūsh (The First of the Biers). αβγδ are known as al-Sarīr السرير (“a bier before the corpse is carried upon it”), Janāzah جنازة (The Corpse) and al-Ḥawḍ الحوض (The Pool). εζη are sometimes singled out specifically as the “girls” who follow the bier, the Banāt (The Girls), or Banāt Nā‘sh (The Girls of the Bier), or Banāt Nā‘sh al-Kubra (The Girls of the Great Bier), or even Banū Na‘sh بنو نعش (Boys of the Bier).

1. Awwal al-Na‘sh (The First One of the Bier): α UMa, Bubhe. It has many other names: Awwal al-Nu‘ūsh (The First of the Bier’s Stars), Awwal al-Na‘sh al-Shāmī (The First Northern One of the Bier), Awwal al-Na‘sh al-Muqaddamayn al-Shamāliyayn (The First of the Two Northernmost of the Bier), Muqaddam al-Na‘sh, Muqaddam al-Nu‘ūsh مقدم النعش (Foremost of the Bier), Muqaddam al-Nu‘ūsh al-Shāmī (Northernmost of the Bier).
2. Thānī al-Na‘sh (The Second One of the Bier): β UMa, Merak. Or Thānī al-Nu‘ūsh (The Second of the Bier’s Stars).
3. Thālith al-Na‘sh (The Third One of the Bier): γ UMa, Phecda, Thālith al-Nu‘ūsh (The Third of the Bier’s Stars) or, according to al-Mahrī, al-Fard (The Solitary one). This and the next star are also known as The Two Limping Ones (al-A‘rajān الأعرجان).
4. al-Khāfi الخافي (The Hidden One): δ UMa, Megrez. Also called Akhīr al-Sarīr أخير السرير (The Last one of the Bier), Rābi‘ al-Na‘sh (The Fourth One of the Bier), Rābi‘ al-Na‘sh al-A‘raj (The Limping Fourth One of the Bier), and simply Rābi‘ al-A‘raj (The Fourth Limping One).
5. al-Ḥawr الحور (The Black-Eyed Beauty): ε UMa, Alioth. Also al-Ḥawar (The Bull), al-Jawn الجون (The Black Horse), and Khāmis al-Na‘sh (The Fifth One of the Bier). It is unclear to what extent the difference between al-Ḥawr and al-Jawn might have been initially a case of *taṣhīf* or scribal corruption. This and the next star, ε and ζ UMa, are sometimes called Hirāb هيراب (The Keel) or Hirāb al-Safīnah السفينة (The Ship’s Keel), referring to a tradition reported by Ibn Mājid, see below, *Safīnat al-Nūḥ*.

6. al-^ʿAnāq العناق (The She-Kid): ζ UMa, Mizar. It has some other names: Sādis al-Na^ʿsh (The Sixth One of the Bier), Sādis al-Nu^ʿūsh (The Sixth of the Bier's Stars), Sādis Nujūm al-Na^ʿsh (The Sixth Star of the Bier).
7. al-Qā'id القائد (The Leader): η UMa, Alkaid, called also Ākhir al-Nu^ʿūsh (The Last Star of the Bier) and Sābi^ʿ al-Na^ʿsh (The Seventh One of the Bier).
8. al-Suhā السها (The Overlooked One): 80 UMa, Alcor, a little star next to the second of the tail. It has two names, al-Ṣaydaq الصيدق (The Trusted One) and al-Nu^ʿaysh النعيش (The Little Bier).
9. Safīnat Nūḥ سفينة نوح (Noah's Ark): γδεζη UMa. A constellation which is superimposed on The Plough and which seems to be described only by Ibn Mājid (*Fawā'id* I, 10–11), explaining that Noah

designed the ship based on the qualities of the five stars of Ursa Major: its stern on the third star, its keel on the fourth, fifth and sixth, and its bow on the seventh star of Ursa Major.

Draco: Dra · al-Tinnīn (The Dragon)

1. al-Tinnīn التنين (The Dragon): this name is used to refer to either the head of the long constellation of The Dragon, νβξγ Dra, or to its tail and northernmost end, which is between Ursa minor and Ursa major, and includes λκ and α Dra. These three, or the latter alone, were called al-Tinnīn by al-Mahrī, and they were identified with the old name of al-Ḥayyah الحية (The Snake). The head was in turn identified by Ibn Mājid with al-^ʿAwā'idh العوائذ (or ^ʿAwā'id, The Mother Camels), see next. The modern name Eltanin is currently used for γ Dra alone.
2. Awwal al-^ʿAwā'idh أول العوائذ (The First of the Mother Camels): ν Dra. Also Muqaddam al-^ʿAwā'idh (The Foremost of the Mother Camels). Al-^ʿAwā'idh is one of the original early Arabic constellations, called sometimes also Ṣalīb al-Wāqi' صليب الواقع (The Cross of Vega, cf. Kunitzsch 108), eventually identified to the head of the Ptolemaic Dragon, γβξν Dra. It appeared in the Renaissance map of Peter Apian as *Quinque dromedarii*.
3. Thānī al-^ʿAwā'idh (The Second of the Mother Camels): β Dra, Rastaban or Alwaid. Its first modern name derives from رأس التنين *ra's al-tinnīn*, “the head of the dragon”.
4. al-^ʿAwḥaqān العوهقان (The Two Black Ravens): ζη Dra, named also al-Dhi'bān الذئبان (The Two Wolves) or al-Ḥurrān الحمران (The Two Young Gazelles). Two stars in the middle body of the Dragon, located between al-^ʿAwā'idh and al-Farqadān.

Corona Borealis: CrB · al-Ḥujrah (The Precinct)

Alternative early names of this constellation include al-Fakkah الفكّة (The Open Ring), Qaṣ'at al-Masākīn قصعة المساكين (The Bowl of the Poor) and Ṣaḥfat al-Masākīn صحفة

المساكين (same meaning).

Muqaddam al-Ḥujrah مقدمّ الحجرّة (The Foremost of the Precinct): α CrB, Alphecca, derived from al-Fakkah. This star is also called Munīr al-Ḥujrah منير الحجرّة (The Bright One of the Precinct), al-Munīr min al-Iklil al-Shamālī (The Bright One of the Northern Crown), al-Najm al-Munīr min al-Fakkah (The Bright Star of al-Fakkah). See *Muʿjam* 358.

Lyra: Lyr · Salyāq/Shalyāq (Lyre) or Silahfāh (Tortoise)

1. Salyāq/Shalyāq شلياق / سلياق (Lyre): β Lyr, Sheliak—also vocalised with a *kasrah* as Silyāq/Shilyāq. This name is used by Ibn Mājid to refer to Deneb as well, creating some puzzling identification issues, see *Muʿjam* 306–306.
2. Ridf al-Wāqi ردف الواقع (The Follower of Vega): ε Lyr. Note that the *ridf* is used for other stars in Lyra and in Cygnus, with a number of variations. See above, [no. 19 of the Brightest Stars](#).

Cygnus: Cyg · al-Dajājah (The Fowl)

1. Ridf al-Ridf ردف الردف (The Follower of the Follower [of the Chicken]): ω or ζ Cyg.

Cassiopeia: Cas · Dhāt al-Kursī (The Lady in a Chair)

In early Arab tradition, portions of Cassiopeia and Andromeda were said to form a constellation called al-Nāqah الناقة (The She-Camel), from which several star names derive.

1. Baṭn al-Nāqah بطن الناقة (The Belly of the She-Camel): β Cas, Caph. Also al-Jamal الجمل (The Camel), al-Sanām السنام (The Hump), Sanām al-Jady سنام الجدي (The Hump of the Kid), Sanām al-Quṭb (The Hump of the Pole), Sanām al-Nāqah (The Hump of the She-camel), Munīr al-nāqah (The Bright One of the She-Camel), al-ʿĪs العيس (The Reddish White Camels), al-Kaff al-Khaḍīb كفّ الخضيب (The Henna-Dyed Hand). Its modern name, Caph, derives from al-Kaff al-Khaḍīb, which sometimes refers to the five brightest stars of Cassiopeia, β α γ δ ε Cas. Sanām al-Nāqah was also used as the name of another group in the same constellation, ζ λ β γ Cas.

Auriga: Aur · Mumsik al-Aʿinnah (The Holder of the Reins)

1. al-Dhubbān الذبّان: β Aur, Menkalinan, or Dhūbbān al-Bār (The Dhubbān of the Devotee), or Dhubbān al-ʿAyyūq (The Dhubbān of the Goat). The word *dhubbān* seems to be a uniquely nautical term, meaning a conventional unit of measure, normally four fingers; see Staples *s.v.*
2. Dhubbān Dhubbān al-ʿAyyūq (The Dhubbān of the Dhubbān of the Goat): θ Aur.

Ophiuchus: Oph · al-Ḥawwāʾ (The Snake Charmer)

1. al-Sābiqān السابقان (The Two Racing Horses): ζ η Oph. The singular form of the noun gave origin to the official modern name of η Oph, Sabik.

Delphinus: Del · Dulfīn (Dolphin)

1. Ṣalīb al-Shām صليب الشام or Ṣalīb al-Shamāl (The Northern Cross): $\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$ Del. This subset of four stars of the Ptolemaic Dolphin was a traditional asterism among the Arabs.

Pegasus: Peg · al-Faras al-Aʿẓam (The Greater Horse)

1. al-Fargh الفرج (The Spout): $\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$ Peg, The Great Square of Pegasus. It must be noted that in contemporary IAU nomenclature, α And is preferred to δ Peg, so this asterism would be $\alpha\beta\gamma$ Peg + α And. It has many other names: al-Farghān الفرغان (The Two Spouts), al-Furūgh الفروع (The Spouts), Furūgh al-Dalū (The Spouts of the Bucket), ʿUrquwat al-Dalū عرقوة الدلو (The Bucket-Carrying Rod). This last name can also refer to a single star, β Peg. Generally, Al-Fargh seems to refer to either one of the two spouts of the well bucket (*al-dalū*). The term alone is not common, but it appears as al-Fargh al-Muqaddam, or al-Fargh al-Muʾakhhir.
2. Awwal al-Fargh (The First One of the Spout): α Peg, Markab. Called also al-Fargh al-Muqaddam al-Janūbī (The Foremost Southern Spout).
3. Awwal al-Fargh al-Shām (The First One of the Northern Spout): β Peg, Scheat, named also Awwal al-Fargh al-Muqaddam al-Shāmī, Jarīm Awwal al-Naʿsh al-Shāmī جریم أول النعش الشامي (The First Massive One of the Northern Bier), al-Muqaddam al-Fargh al-Shāmī (The Foremost of the Northern Spout).
4. Akhīr Fargh al-Shām (The Last One of the Northern Spout): δ Peg, Alpheratz (nowadays α And, as mentioned above). Other names include al-Fargh al-Shāmī al-Muʾakhhar (The Posterior Northern Spout), al-Fargh al-Muʾakhhar al-Shāmī (The Posterior Northern Spout), al-Fargh al-Muʾakhhar al-Shāmālī (The Posterior Northern Spout), Fam al-Faras فم الفرس (The Mouth of the Horse), Fam al-Nāqah فم الناقة (The Mouth of the She-Camel).
5. al-Fargh al-Shamālī (The Northern Spout): α And + β Peg, Alpheratz and Scheat. Also al-Farghān al-Shamālīyān (The Two Northern Spouts), or al-Shamālīyān (The Two Northern Ones).
6. al-Najmān al-Janūbiyān min al-Farghayn (The Two Southern Stars of the Two Spouts): $\alpha\gamma$ Peg, Markab and Algenib. Also al-Janūbiyān الجنوبيان (The Two Southern Ones).
7. Saʿd al-Humām سعد الهمام (The Auspice of the Aspiring One): $\zeta\eta$ Peg.

Andromeda: And · al-Marʿāt al-Musalsalah (The Chained Woman)

1. Fuʿād al-Hūt فؤاد الحوت (The Liver of the Fish): β And, Mirach. This is the same as lunar station 28, Baṭn al-Hūt, [see above](#).

4.2 The Southern Constellations

Cetus: Cet · Qīṭus

1. al-Ḍifdiʿ al-Thānī الضفدع الثاني (The Second Frog): β Cet, Diphda.

Orion: Ori · al-Jawzāʾ; al-Jabbār (The Giant)

An alternative name for this constellation, used by al-Mahrī, is al-Mīzān الميزان (The Balance).

1. Tāj al-Dhawāʾib الذوائب تاج (The Crown of Curls): $15(\gamma^2)$, $11(\gamma')$ $0^{\circ}2\pi^{1-6}\delta\epsilon$ Ori, called also simply either al-Tāj or al-Dhawāʾib. It refers to a string of little stars west of the main frame of Orion, resembling a “flowing lock of hair”.
2. al-Naẓm النظم (The String of Pearls): $\delta\epsilon\zeta$ Ori. Also al-Niẓām النظام, with the same meaning, al-Safāfid السفافيد (The Skewers), and Mintaqah al-Jawzāʾ منطقة الجوزاء (The Belt of Jawzāʾ), whence the modern name Mintaka for δ Ori. Sometimes al-Naẓm is used to refer to the whole of Orion. Awwal al-Naẓm is sometimes used to refer to ζ Ori, Alnitak, alone.
3. al-Marāzim المرآزم: $\alpha\beta\kappa\gamma$ Ori, or Marāzim al-Jawzāʾ. The square of the four bright stars in Orion, i.e. the shoulders and feet of The Giant. *Marāzim* is a plural form of *Mirzam*, meaning unknown.
4. Marāzim al-Jawzāʾ al-Awwalān: $\beta\gamma$ Ori, Rigel and Bellatrix, The First Two Mirzams of Jawzāʾ.
5. al-Mirzamān or al-Mirzamān al-Zawāhir المرزمان الزواهر: $\alpha\beta$ Ori. The Two Mirzams, or The Two Bright Mirzams, a group name for the two brightest stars in Orion.

Canis Minor: CMi · al-Kalb al-Aṣghar (The Lesser Dog)

1. al-Dhirāʿ al-Ghumayṣāʾ الذراع الغميصاء (The Bleary-eyed Foreleg): $\alpha\beta$ CMi, Procyon and Gomeisa. Other names are al-Dhirāʿ al-Yamānī (The Southern Foreleg), al-Dhirāʿ al-Maqbūḍah الذراع المقبوضة (The Drawn-up Foreleg), al-Yad al-Maqbūḍah (The Clenched Hand). Some associate al-Ghumayṣāʾ (The Bleary-eyed One) with this pair, but it seems to refer more appropriately to Procyon alone; see [above](#), [no. 8](#) of the Brightest Stars.

Centaurus: Cen · al-Qinṭūrus

1. al-Ḥimārān الحماران (The Two Donkeys): $\alpha\beta$ Cen, al-Wazn (The Measuring Weight) and Ḥaḍār, that is Rigil Kentaurus and Hadar, usually associated in Arab uranography with Suhayl. They are called also al-ʿIraqān عراقان (The Two Borders/Roots?), al-ʿAmūdān العمودان (The Two Columns), al-Fārisān الفارسان (The Two Horses), al-Miṣḥalān المسحلان (The Two Knives), al-Ḥiṣnān الحصنان (The Two Fortresses), al-Muḥalfān المحلفان (The Two Bound by Oath), al-Muḥannithān المحنّثان (The Two

Oath-Breakers); for this last name, see Brightest Stars no. 8, above, and Staples 395.
 2. Rukbah Qintūrus رُكْبَةُ قِنْتُورُس (The Knee of the Centaur): β Cen.

Corvus: Crv · al-Ghurāb (The Crow)

1. Anjum al-Ghurāb أُنْجُمُ الْغُرَاب (The Crow Stars): αβγδε Crv.

Puppis: Pup · al-Kawthal (The Stern)

1. Dhubbān Suhayl ذُبَّانُ سُهَيْل (The Dhubbān of Canopus): τ Pup. In spite of its name, and as observed by Staples (409, 432), the distance between this star and Canopus is not four fingers, so the identification remains uncertain.

Crux: Cru · Ṣalīb al-Janūb (The Cross of the South) or al-Murabbaʿ (The Square)

1. al-Ṣalīb al-Janūbī الصَّالِيبُ الْجَنُوبِي (The Southern Cross): αβγδ Cru. Other appellations for it are Ṣalīb al-Janūb (The Cross of the South), Ṣalīb al-Quṭb (The Cross of the Pole), Ṣalīb al-Yaman (The Cross of the South), al-Murabbaʿāt المُرَبَّعَات (The Ones of the Square).
2. al-Murabbaʿ al-Fawqānī (The Upper Squared One): γ Cru. Named also: al-Murabbaʿ al-Fawqī (same meaning), Najm al-Murabbaʿ al-Fawqī (The Upper Squared Star), Fawqiyat al-Murabbaʿ (The Upper One of the Square), al-Fūqānī (The Upper One).
3. al-Murabbaʿān al-Awsatān (The Two Middle Ones of the Square): βδ Cru. They have many other names: al-Murabbaʿān (The Two of the Square), al-Najmān al-Awsatān min al-Murabbaʿ (The Two Middle Stars of the Square), al-Murabbaʿ al-Awsat (The Middle Square), al-Murabbaʿ al-Wusaṭ (The Middle Square), al-Murabbaʿ al-Wuṣṭānī (same meaning), Nujūm Wasaṭ al-Murabbaʿ (The Middle Stars of the Square), al-Awsatān min al-Murabbaʿ (The Two Middle Ones from the Square).
4. al-Murabbaʿān al-Taḥṭiyān (The Lower Ones of the Square): αβ Cru.

5 Magellanic Clouds

Their joint name is al-Ghamāmah الغمامة (The Veil), or al-Saḥāb السحاب (The Cloud), al-Saḥāʾib السحاب (The Clouds), or al-Saḥābatān al-Janūbiyyatān السحابتان الجنوبيتان (The Two Southern Clouds). They consist of two nebulae:

1. al-Saḥābah al-Baydāʾ السحابة البيضاء or al-Bīd البيض (The White Cloud): Large Magellanic Cloud, LMC; Nubecula Major, or the Greater Little Cloud.
2. al-Saḥābah al-Sawdāʾ السحابة السوداء or al-Saḥāyib al-Sawdāʾ, or al-Sawdāʾ: Small Magellanic Cloud, SMC; Nubecula Minor, or Lesser Little Cloud.

6 Addendum: Other Useful Celestial Objects

Other stars or combinations of celestial objects mentioned by Ibn Mājid and al-Mahri.

1. al-Qafazāt القفزة (The Leaps): $\kappa\lambda\mu\nu\xi$ UMa. Also called Qafazāt al-Zibā' (The Leaps of the Gazelles) or Qafazāt al-Zabī (The Leaps of the Gazelle), these are three pairs of smaller stars south of Ursa Major, marking the footprints of the gazelles as they leap.
2. al-Qafazat al-Ulā القفزة الأولى (The First Leap): $\xi\nu$ UMa, or simply al-Ulā.
3. al-Qafazat al-Wuṣṭá القفزة الوسطى (The Middle Leap): $\mu\lambda$ UMa.
4. Ḥawḍ al-Zibā' حوض الظباء (The Pool of the Gazelles): $\tau\theta\varphi\theta\epsilon\zeta$ UMa. With some discrepancies, most authors agree that they are a number, usually seven, of smaller stars west of the brighter part of Ursa Major.
5. al-Zibā' الظباء (The Gazelles): $o\pi\sigma^1\sigma^2$ UMa. A group of even smaller stars west of their Pool.
6. Awāsiṭ al-Nu'ūsh أواسط النعوش (The Middle Ones of the Biers): $\gamma\delta\epsilon$ UMa, Phecda, Megrez, Alioth. Very literally, a group comprising the middle brighter stars of Ursa Major; mentioned as such in Ibn Mājid's poems.
7. al-Fāriṭān الفرطان (The Two Preceding Ones): $\nu\theta$ UMa. The identification varies, also to include o UM, but according to the sources it refers to two stars that “precede” the Bier on their way to dig the grave. This sub-group overlaps partly with al-Zibā' and al-Ḥawḍ.
8. al-Mīkh الميخ (The Nail): γ Cep, Errai. This seems to be an exclusively nautical name, also specified as Mīkh al-Jāh (The Nail of Polaris) or Mīkh al-Judday (same meaning). Ibn Mājid explains the name of this star which is of great practical importance: “this name is of Persian origin, it means a nail (*mismār*), because it fixes Polaris to the Celestial Pole” (IV, 116).
9. al-Thawālith الثوالث (The Triads): this name refers to two pairs of northern and southern circumpolar stars; together with their respective pole, each of these pairs forms a triad or ternary. They are β Cas and γ UMa for the North Pole, and β Cen and α PsA for the South Pole.
10. Sa'd al-Bāri' سعد البارع (The Omen of the Skilled One): $\lambda\mu$ Peg.
11. al-A'lām الأعلام, or Tawābi' al-Ayyūq (The Signs, or Followers of Capella): $\beta\theta\gamma$ Aur, though sometimes identified as $\beta\gamma$ Aur. Note that in our current nomenclature, β Tau is preferred over γ Aur.
12. Dhanab al-Ḥūt ذنب الحوت (The Tail of the Fish): γ Gru, Aldhanab, is the most likely match, but there are variations, and Khoury associates it at some point with “any star in the tail of the Southern Fish”. It must be noted that the modern constellation Grus used to be the “tail” of Piscis Austrinus, al-Ḥūt al-Janūbī.

13. al-Majarraḥ المجرة (The Track / The Watercourse): The Milky Way. Apart from its use to determine the relative positions of a number of stars and asterisms, Ibn Mājid explains (*Fawā'id* IV, 149–50) that the Milky Way is useful to understand the basics of the movement of the spheres—we might say, “principles of cosmography”.

7 Bibliography

There are a number of “nationally sponsored” nautical ephemerides, along the lines of the British *Nautical Almanac* mentioned above, which have a selection of stars for navigation. The French *Ephémérides nautiques*, published by the [Bureau des longitudes](#), use 27 stars. The *Nautical Almanac* itself, published by [HM Nautical Almanac Office](#), uses 57 stars. The Russian set included in the *Nautical Astronomical Almanac* (Морской астрономический альманах) includes 160 stars and a reduced set of 77; it is published bi-annually by the The Institute of Applied Astronomy of the Russian Academy of Sciences. In the present Technical Note we are including 111 stars, asterisms and celestial objects which combine in various ways a total of 155 stars.

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7.3 Websites

- Celestial Navigation Net, by Mary Taylor.
- History of Astronomy, by Robert Harry van Gent, especially his handy reference for al-Ṣūfī’s constellations.
- Lisbon Arabic Science & Philosophy Reading Group, a blog by Inês Bénard and Juan Acevedo.
- The Manuchihr Globe, on a 17th-century Khorasanian celestial globe.

Two Deserts, One Sky, by Danielle Adams.

7.4 Video

Adams, Danielle. 2020. "Multivalent Textures of Arabian Astronomy." *Meet an Astronomer* Series, Lowell Observatory, Arizona.

Astronomical Index

Star names in Bayer notation, sorted in alphabetical order by constellation.

Andromeda

α And: Akhīr Fargh al-Shām

α And + β Peg: al-Fargh al-Shamālī

β And: Baṭn al-Ḥūt

β And: Fu'ād al-Ḥūt

Aquarius

α Aqr: Sa'd al-Malik

$\beta\xi$ Aqr + λ Cap: Sa'd al-Su'ūd

$\gamma\pi\zeta\eta$ Aqr: Sa'd al-Akhbiyah

$\nu\mu\epsilon$ Aqr: Sa'd Bula'

Aquila

α Aql: Altair: al-Ṭā'ir

Aries

α Ari: Fard al-Sharaṭayn

$\alpha\beta$ Ari (also $\alpha\beta\gamma$): al-Sharaṭān

$\epsilon\delta\rho$ Ari: al-Buṭayn

$41(c)$ Ari: Awwal Adlā' al-Ḥamal

$41(c)$, 39, 35, 33 Ari: al-Adlā'

Auriga

α Aur, Capella: al-'Ayyūq

β Aur: al-Dhubbān

$\beta\theta\gamma$ Aur: al-A'lām

θ Aur: Dhubbān Dhubbān al-'Ayyūq

Boötes

α Boo, Arcturus: al-Simāk al-Rāmiḥ

Capricorn

$\alpha\beta$ Cap: Sa'd al-Dhābiḥ

$\gamma\delta$ Cap: Sa'd al-nāshirah

Carina

α Car, Canopus: Suhayl

Cassiopeia

β Cas: Baṭn al-Nāqah

β Cas + γ UMa: al-Thawālith

Centaurus

$\alpha\beta$ Cen: al-Ḥimār

$\alpha\beta$ Cen: al-Ḥimārān

α Cen: al-Ma'qil

β Cen, Hadar or Agena: al-Ma'qil

β Cen, Hadar or Agena: Ḥaḍār

β Cen, Hadar or Agena: Rukbah Qinqūrus

Cetus

β Cet: al-Ḍifdi' al-Thānī

Cepheus

γ Cep, Errai: al-Mikh

Canis Major

α CMa, Sirius: al-Shi'rá

Canis Minor

α CMi, Procyon: al-Shi'rá al-Shāmīyah

$\alpha\beta$ CMi: al-Dhirā' al-Ghumayṣā'

Cancer

ϵ Cnc, Praesepe: al-Nathrah

χ Cnc + λ Leo: al-Ṭarf

Canes Venatici

α CVn, Cor Caroli: al-Fu'ād

Corona Borealis

α CrB, Alphecca: Muqaddam al-Ḥujrah

Corvus

$\alpha\beta\gamma\delta\epsilon$ Crv: Anjum al-Ghurāb

Crux

α Cru, Acrux: al-Murabba'

$\alpha\beta$ Cru: al-Murabba'ān al-Taḥṭiyān

$\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$ Cru, Southern Cross: al-Ṣalīb al-Janūbī

β Cru, Mimosa: Najm al-Ṣalīb al-Sharqī

$\beta\delta$ Cru: al-Murabba'ān al-Awsaṭān

γ Cru, Gacrux: al-Murabba' al-Fawqānī

ϵ Cru: al-Maghribiyāt al-Murabba'

Cygnus

α Cyg, Deneb: al-Ridf

ω or ζ Cyg: Ridf al-Ridf

Delphinus

$\alpha\beta\gamma\delta$ Del: \mathcal{S} alib al-Shām

Draco

β Dra: Thānī al-‘Awā’idh

$\zeta\eta$ Dra: al-‘Awḥaqān

ν Dra: Awwal al-‘Awā’idh

$\nu\beta\zeta\gamma$ Dra: al-Tinnīn

Eridanus

α Eri, Achernar: al-Muḥannith

Gemini

α Gem, Castor: Shāmī al-Dhirā‘ al-Shāmī

$\alpha\beta$ Gem, Castor and Pollux: al-Dhirā‘

β Gem, Pollux: Ra’s al-Taw’am al-Mu’akhhkar

$\gamma\eta\mu\nu\xi$ Gem (also $\gamma\xi$ Gem): al-Han‘ah

Grus

γ Gru, Aldhanab: Dhanab al-Ḥūt

Leo

β Leo: al-Ṣarfah

$\delta\nu$ Leo: al-Zubrah

$\zeta\gamma\eta\alpha$ Leo: al-Jabhah

Libra

$\alpha\beta$ Lib: al-Zubānā

Lyra

α Lyr, Vega: al-Kāsir

β Lyr, Sheliak: Salyāq

ϵ Lyr: Ridf al-Wāqī‘

Magellanic Clouds

Large Magellanic Cloud: al-Saḥābah al-Bayḍā’

Small Magellanic Cloud: al-Saḥābah al-Sawḍā’

Messier Objects

Messier 7, Ptolemy Cluster: al-Ibrah

Messier 44, Praesepe: al-Nathrah

Messier 45, the Pleiades: al-Thurayyā

The Milky Way

The Milky Way: al-Majarrah

Ophiuchus

$\zeta\eta$ Oph: al-Sābiqān

Orion

$\alpha\beta$ Ori: al-Mirzamān

$\alpha\beta\chi\gamma$ Ori: al-Marāzim

β Ori, Rigel: al-Nājid al-Barrāq

$\beta\gamma$ Ori: Marāzim al-Jawzā’ al-Awwalān

γ Ori, Bellatrix (also α Ori): al-Mirzam

$\delta\epsilon\zeta$ Ori: al-Nazm

$15(\gamma^2)$, $11(\gamma')$ $\circ^2\pi^{1-6}\delta\epsilon$ Ori: Tāj al-Dhawā’ib

$\lambda\phi$ Ori: al-Haq‘ah

Pegasus

α Peg, Markab: Awwal al-Fargh

α Peg + α And: al-Najmān al-Janūbiyān min al-Farghayn

β Peg, Scheat: Awwal al-Fargh al-Shām

$\alpha\beta\gamma$ Peg+ α And: al-Fargh

$\alpha\beta$ Peg: al-Fargh al-Muqaddam

γ Peg + α And: al-Fargh al-Mu’akhhkar

$\zeta\zeta$ Peg: Sa’d al-Humām

$\lambda\mu$ Peg: Sa’d al-Bārī‘

Piscis Austrinus

α PisA, Fomalhaut: Ākhir al-Nahr

Puppis

τ Pup: Dhubbān Suhayl

Sagittarius

γ Sgr: al-Sahm

$\gamma\delta\epsilon\eta$ Sgr: al-Na‘ā’im al-Wāridah

π Sgr: al-Baldah

$\gamma\delta\epsilon\eta\sigma\phi\tau\zeta$ Sgr: al-Na‘ā’im

σ Sgr: Taḥtat al-Qaws

$\sigma\phi\zeta\tau$ Sgr: al-Ṣādirah

ϕ Sgr: Sahm al-Awwal

$\tau\nu\psi\omega A\zeta$ Sgr: al-Qilādah

Scorpius

α Sco, Antares: al-Qalb

$\beta\delta\pi$ Sco: al-Iklīl

λ Sco, Shaula: al-Shawlah

$\lambda\sigma\tau\lambda\nu$ Sco: al-Shawlah

Taurus

α Tau, Aldebaran: al-Dabarān

β Tau (?), Elnath: Kalbā al-Dabarān
 χν Tau: al-Ḍayqah
 Hyades: Qalā'is

Ursa Major

α UMa, Bubhe: Awwal al-Na'sh
 β UMa, Merak: Thānī al-Na'sh
 γ UMa, Phed: Thālith al-Na'sh
 γδε UMa: Awāsīt al-Nu'ūsh
 γδεζη UMa: Safīnat Nūḥ
 δ UMa, Megrez: al-Khāfī (The hidden)
 ε UMa: al-Ḥawr
 ζ UMa: al-'Anāq
 η UMa, Alkaid: al-Qā'id
 ικλμνξ UMa: al-Qafazāt
 μλ UMa: al-Qafazāt al-Wuṣṭá
 ξν UMa: al-Qafazāt al-Ulá

οδπσ¹σ² UMa: al-Zibā'
 τηυφθεφ UMa: Ḥawḍ al-Zibā'
 υθ UMa: al-Fāriṭān
 8ο UMa, Alcor: al-Suhā

Ursa Minor

α UMi, Polaris: al-Jāh
 β UMi, Kochab: al-Farqad al-Kabīr
 γ UMi: al-Farqad al-Ṣaghīr
 βγ UMi: al-Farqadān

Virgo

α Vir, Spica: al-Simāk al-A'zal
 βηγδε Vir: al-'Awwā'
 γ Vir: Zāwiyat al-'Awwā'
 ε Vir: Ākhir al-'Awwā'
 ιχλ Vir: al-Ghafr
 ο Vir: Awwal al-'Awwā'

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